

Progress in Citizen Engagement and Digital Participation: Contributions from the TU Delft Citizen Voice Initiative

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The Citizen Voice team encourages academics, practitioners, community organisers, and students to engage with, critique, and build upon the ideas presented in this document. For any inquiries, please contact J.E.Goncalves@tudelft.nl.

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Introduction

Debates about public participation and civic engagement urban governance have been evolving since the 50s and 60s, decades marked by significant social upheavals with various social movements emerging in cities during, influencing politics, civil rights, and cultural attitudes. One of the early thinkers in the field was Sherry Arnstein, whose seminal paper “A Ladder of Citizen Participation” (1969) laid the groundwork for understanding power dynamics within participation processes. Arnstein opens the paper by comparing citizen participation with eating spinach: “no one is against it in principle because it is good for you”. The reason why participation is deemed good in theory is because it is usually associated with democratic ideas, and generally no one thinks that democracy is not desirable. She then moves on to argue that the support for participation is reduced to “polite handclaps” when this principle is advocated by the “have-nots”. The have-nots being the ones excluded from planning, cutting across gender, class, and race.

Another important contribution of this time was the concept of ‘the right to the city’, articulated by the French philosopher Henri Lefebvre (1968), emphasising the idea that all citizens have the right to produce and reproduce the city according to their needs and aspirations. Lefebvre highlights the importance of spatial politics and urges spatial scholars and practitioners to recognise the dynamic nature of spatial production and move beyond static views of space. This implies understanding space and the city as a continuous site of political struggle and social production. In this light, the right to the city is “a

collective rather than an individual right since changing the city inevitably depends upon the exercise of a collective power over the processes of urbanisation” (Harvey, 2008).

These critiques did not happen in a vacuum. They were prompted by and intertwined with social movements at the time and led to a real shift in planning from top-down to more collaborative and empowering models of participation. In the 70s, advocacy planning emerged (Paul Davidoff, 1965) emphasising the need for planners to advocate for the interests of marginalised and disenfranchised communities. This was followed by communicative planning (Healey, 1997; Innes, 1995) and deliberative planning (Forester, 1999), which further advanced participatory ideals through consensus-building, structured discourse, and deliberative practices.

The formalisation of participatory ideals gained further momentum with initiatives such as the 1992 Local Agenda 21 at the Rio Earth Summit, promoting collaborative and communicative planning approaches. Around 2010, the United Nations began incorporating inclusive urbanisation as a core element of its sustainable development agenda, recognising cities as key actors in achieving global development objectives. Nowadays, the importance of creating inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities is enshrined as Goal 11 in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

However, despite this rich history, the implementation of participatory processes remains uneven and frequently symbolic, often co-opted

by technocratic agendas that frame participation as a depoliticised exercise. This technocratic framing can lead to the marginalisation of alternative voices and reinforce existing power structures rather than disrupt them (Gooch et al. 2015; Goncalves et al., 2024).

Within complex and highly unequal spaces such as the city, engaging citizens and other local groups is by no means a trivial task. Urban decision-makers, planners and designers require specific methodologies and tools to understand the diverse needs and aspirations of various groups and address the practical challenges and value conflicts that emerge from this complexity. From a citizen-perspective, too, innovative methods and approaches are necessary to enable citizens and communities to voice their opinions in ways that are appropriate to them, beyond conventional methods such as public hearings. This is linked to a relatively recent growing interest in the role of arts, rituals, and cultural practices in addressing the spiralling socio-ecological crises unfolding today and affecting people and communities worldwide (Gabrys & Yusoff, 2012; Fotaki et al., 2020; Machen et al., 2023; Berger et al., 2024). Contributions in this direction may help to contest existing power dynamics and create the conditions for real transformative interventions in the world (Yusoff & Gabrys, 2011; Paproki, 2020).

Literature shows that digital participation tools can also support engagement processes, given their potential to enable remote participation and reach a large number of citizens (Kahila-Tani, Broberg, et al. 2016; Kahila-Tani, Kytta, and Geertman 2019). However, digital tools for citizen engagement are usually designed from a top-down expert perspective without considering how citizens

interact with technology (Gooch et al. 2015; Biedermann et al. 2023), potentially deepening the digital divide and leading to adverse effects such as the rejection of technology altogether. Moreover, most digital tools available are generic, failing to address the specificity of particular contexts, target groups, and planning needs (Goncalves et al., 2025, forthcoming). Therefore, although opportunities brought about by digitalisation are promising, various challenges need to be addressed to ensure the inclusive and meaningful adoption of digital tools in urban decision-making (Goncalves et al., 2024).

The TU Delft Citizen Voice Initiative emerged in 2021 as a bottom-up research group to engage critically with the issues described above, aiming to empower communities in urban planning and design through inclusive and meaningful participation and open data practices. This report documents the research and activities carried out by Citizen Voice between 2021 and 2025. It starts presenting the initiative, the team, and the journey so far. This is followed by an overview of the research projects developed during this period – ranging from qualitative studies to design and arts-based approaches, as well as community-based and transdisciplinary research. It then reflects on the impact achieved and concludes with a set of ethical guidelines that emerged from these experiences, which respond to particular ethical challenges of working with communities and digital platforms.

1

About Citizen Voice

This chapter introduces and describes the Citizen Voice initiative. It starts by explaining its mission, values, and the research method adopted in all projects. Following, it presents a summary of our journey from the start in 2021 to the present year 2025. Finally, it presents an overview of the key research findings collected by the initiative so far.

What is Citizen Voice?

Citizen Voice started in 2021 from the bottom and has grown organically until today, receiving support from various institutions within and outside TU Delft. Citizen Voice works with three core principles:

1. Inclusive and situated participation,
2. Creative and design-based methodologies,
3. Transdisciplinary and open research practices.

We recognise participation as a deeply political endeavour and have a critical perspective on the power dynamics within participation processes. We also emphasise the importance of actionable insights and innovative tools and methods that support practitioners in the field and citizens in real life. This dual perspective is encapsulated in our unique **critical action research**.

Over the past four years, we have been conducting research projects to understand how citizens and communities perceive their environment. We have developed digital tools, interactive prototypes, and art exhibitions to engage citizens and communities in complex topics such as climate change and urban biodiversity. Through this participatory research approach, we deepen the understanding of how citizens and communities perceive their environment and how they interact with technologies.

We also engage critically with current trends in public participation and citizen engagement, including the increasing implementation of digital tools and artificial intelligence in urban governance, planning and design. By doing so, we seek to understand how technology shapes space and social

relations in cities. Citizen Voice stands by the imperative that technology development needs to move away from the idea of one-size-fits-all towards a situated approach that considers the socio-spatial context in which technology is embedded. In addition to understanding technological trends, we also develop open software and ethical guidelines for transdisciplinary collaborations, aiming to counterbalance the increasing commodification of urban technologies and data and fostering healthy collaborative research environments.

Highlights

- Citizen Voice aims to empower communities by promoting inclusive and meaningful participation in urban planning and design.
- Citizen Voice engages critically with technology and examines how digital tools shape urban spaces and social relations, advocating for situated approaches over one-size-fits-all solutions.
- Citizen Voice uses creative, transdisciplinary methods to capture diverse perspectives often overlooked in traditional urban data.
- Citizen Voice is committed to open science, ensuring all tools and knowledge are open-source to support democratic and just urban development.

Research Approach

Citizen Voice follows an iterative research approach grounded in the principles of **Critical Action Research**, a participatory and reflexive methodology that integrates action and inquiry to confront and transform

The meaning of our logo

Our logo represents four people sharing one head, symbolizing collective thinking and unity. We believe it reflects the nature and values of our initiative, as we produce knowledge for the collective and tackle complex issues collaboratively. A key strength of Citizen Voice is its horizontal organization: we make decisions together, and every team member has a voice.

Figure 1: Citizen Voice's logo.

power imbalances and injustices within specific social contexts. In our design-based projects, we built on repeated cycles of research, design, and testing. Each cycle begins with a research phase, which includes literature review, data collection, and a moment of critical reflection on the insights gathered. This phase also includes context analysis to ensure that social and spatial local aspects are considered in our design. The research phase is followed by a design phase, where we collaboratively prototype

new artifacts informed by research insights. In the testing phase, we expose our designs to citizens, inviting them to engage with the prototypes, gathering feedback that not only informs design improvements but also contributes to broader discussions about the local environment. This continuous, participatory loop enables us to progressively refine our designs while advancing our research and promoting meaningful and context-aware change.

Figure 2: Critical action research.

The team

Citizen Voice consists of an interdisciplinary team at the intersection of urbanism, participatory design, and software development. We also constantly interact with urban stakeholders outside academia, including citizens and communities, policymakers, and practitioners, operating within a truly transdisciplinary environment.

Juliana Gonçalves
Founder and Project Lead

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Expert Participation

Carissa Champlin
Expert Participation

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Johanna Zehntner
Research Assistant

Drew Harris
Research Assistant

Milou Mulder
Research Assistant

Our journey

Over the past four years, Citizen Voice has been active in leading various research projects.

Collaborations and funding

Citizen Voice has received support from various organisations, including:

- the TU Delft Digital Competence Center,
- the SPRING program of the Convergence Alliance,
- the TU Delft Climate Action Program, the Resilient Delta Initiative,
- the Dutch Research Council (NWO - CIVILIAN project),
- and Horizon Innovation Actions (grant agreement n°101096405).

A Special Collaboration: TU Delft Digital Competence Centre

The Digital Competence Centre (DCC) at TU Delft has been supporting the Citizen Voice initiative, particularly in the development and implementation of the Citizen Mapping Tool and in the CIVILIAN dashboard. They assisted in planning, designing and implementing

software applications, securing funding for the development of our digital tools, and played a crucial role in ensuring our tools are open source and they adhere to the FAIR principles.

DCC members acted as representatives of Citizen Voice during our collaborations with software developers. Their expertise has helped to better communicate our ambitions and needs to software developers that worked in the projects. With their help our digital toolset has been extended in number and in quality, and it has grown our ambitions to provide professional research tools for citizen participation.

The collaboration with DCC emphasizes our commitment to open science and community-driven technological solutions.

Research insights

This chapter synthesises the main lessons learned from Citizen Voice projects and provides concrete recommendations for engaging citizens in climate action through digital technologies. Drawing from both project outcomes and the researchers' experience in the initiative, the chapter also offers a reflection on the challenges of fostering citizen engagement in climate-related planning and design through open science.

Climate communication

Findings from across the Citizen Voice projects highlight the importance of effective climate communication in citizen engagement. They show that simplifying complex climate

information is essential to make content accessible to diverse audiences. Approaches such as personas, storytelling, and relatable examples can help bridge the gap between expert knowledge and public understanding. Additionally, our research shows that most people struggle to connect short-term actions to long-term climate goals, revealing a need to clearly link individual efforts with broader environmental outcomes in platform communication. Furthermore, balancing pessimistic and realistic framings of climate change proved to be essential, as it can foster better citizen engagement. Moreover, arts and design-based methods emerged as vital tools in making abstract climate issues tangible and

Figure 3: Juliana Gonçalves presenting our research insights during the Citizen Voice Launch Event.

Selin Kubilay & Manuel Garcia Alvarez

“At the Digital Competence Center (DCC), we are proud to support the Citizen Voice initiative because of its commitment to the development of open source tools for advancing research on citizen participation. Our collaboration produced open science and community-driven solutions which reflect our dedication to advancing open, reproducible, and collaborative research practices that empower communities and foster innovation.”

emotionally resonant, allowing citizens to explore climate challenges through intuitive, experiential engagement. Another key insight is the importance of clearly communicating the purpose of participation platforms: when citizens are uncertain about why they are engaging with the digital tools, it negatively affects transparency, ownership, and expectation management.

Process challenges

The Citizen Voice projects revealed several systemic challenges in public participation, including issues of accountability, ownership, accessibility, responsiveness, and continuity. A major insight is the importance of tailoring participation methods to different user groups and contexts, which often requires combining digital and physical formats (Goncalves et al., 2024). Despite growing institutional interest in public input, tensions persist between genuine co-creation and top-down governance structures that treat participation as a checkbox activity (Goncalves et al., 2024). This raises a deeper question about the purpose of participation itself, whether it serves democratic inclusion or remains a technocratic means to pre-defined ends. Thus, designing meaningful participation requires reflecting on power dynamics and being open to bottom-up influence (Goncalves et al., 2024).

Digital requirements

Digital technologies are central to many Citizen Voice projects. In all of them and in our research, a user-centric approach repeatedly proved necessary for designing participation platforms. Tools need to be intuitive, accessible, and engaging, with interactive features and attractive visuals that help make climate action feel more tangible and

approachable (Goncalves et al., 2024). However, ethical and legal issues surrounding data collection, storage, and usage hinder trust in digital participation platforms. For this reason, transparency in data governance is essential. Giving “data back” to citizens is a possible way to ensure transparency in citizen engagement, not only to improve trust but also to reinforce citizens’ sense of agency and control. Moreover, we learnt from our projects that citizens value not just connection with institutions but also connection with one another. This points to a frequently overlooked dimension: multi-way citizen-to-citizen communication. Such networks can foster collective learning and action, with the potential to amplify the impact of participation efforts.

Transdisciplinary collaboration

The interdisciplinary nature of this work, at the intersection of urban planning, human-computer interaction, and open science, requires genuine transdisciplinary collaboration. However, this is often misinterpreted as outreach rather than essential. In Citizen Voice projects, arts-based and design-led engagement strategies played a central role in generating research insights. Future work will focus on legitimizing and supporting creative methodologies and move beyond traditional research frameworks. Additionally, through the Citizen Voice projects, a lack of collaboration between urban planners and human-computer interaction experts became clear, resulting in digital participation tools that fail to meet citizen needs. Urban planning often focuses on institutional frameworks and governance mechanisms, overlooking the usability and accessibility of platforms. Bridging this gap requires intentional transdisciplinary collaboration to develop tools that

Figure 4: The Citizen Voice team.

are both technically sound and contextually relevant.

Sustainability over time

One of the most pressing challenges faced by Citizen Voice is the sustainability of engagement and open resources beyond short-term project funding. Led primarily by early-career researchers, the initiative has depended on seed funding for pilots. However, without long-term institutional support, it is difficult to maintain non-extractive citizen collaboration or to preserve open-access outputs like repositories. To address this, funding bodies must go beyond initial support and embed successful pilots into broader research frameworks. Ensuring continuity also means recognising participation as a long-term process, not a one-time event, and securing the resources and institutional commitment necessary for it to thrive.

2

Projects

This chapter explains the projects developed by the Citizen Voice initiative. For each project, the goal, the research and design process, and the final output are described.

2.1

No-one size-fits-all

Team members:

Juliana Gonçalves
Ioannis Ioannou
Trivik Verma

Goal

Public participation has become an integral part of urban governance, offering citizens the opportunity to influence planning and decision-making processes (Kahila-Tani, et al., 2016; Kahila-Tani, et al., 2019). With the increasing role of digital technologies, participatory practices are no longer limited to traditional hearings or workshops but extend to online platforms and interactive tools. However, participation is a complex and contested domain: challenges of inclusivity, representation, and power imbalances often undermine its democratic potential (Alejandro Leal, 2007; Fung, 2015; Mattern, n.d.; Monno & Khakee, 2012). At the same time, digital platforms introduce their own set of opportunities that can enhance accessibility, engagement, and inclusivity, and of challenges that can influence the effectiveness

and trustworthiness of participatory processes. The quality of information gathered through digital technologies depends on factors like sample size, sampling methods, bias, and accuracy (Brown, 2012; Brown & Kyttä, 2014). At the same time, barriers such as unequal access to technology, the need for training, costs, and broader socio-political conditions make it harder to implement and use digital participation tools effectively (Fung, 2015). Recognizing that there is no universal approach, this research investigates how different urban actors, governance professionals, academics, and citizens, perceive participation and digital platforms, aiming to identify guidelines and frameworks that make participation more effective, inclusive, and context-sensitive.

Research and process

In this study, we focused on three main topics: the complexity of public participation in urban governance, what constitutes effective participation, and the role of digital platforms in participation. We combined multiple methods to capture perspectives from three diverse actor groups: local governance, academia, and citizens. First, three workshops with local governance actors explored the challenges of public participation, the requirements for digital tools, and practical issues related to platform design and data management. Second, six semi-structured interviews with

academics provided critical reflections on participation effectiveness, inclusivity, and the potential of digital technologies, while also highlighting trade-offs between openness, privacy, and trust. Third, a citizen survey with 260 respondents investigated how people experience and evaluate participation, what factors motivate or discourage their engagement, and which platform features they consider essential. Finally, a survey of more than 150 existing participatory platforms was conducted to situate these insights within the broader landscape of digital civic technologies.

2. Guidelines for designing digital participation platforms

- 2.1. take a user-centric approach;
- 2.2. develop user-friendly interfaces to ensure intuitive navigation and an easy-to-use experience;
- 2.3. provide opportunities for stakeholder exchange and dialogue;
- 2.4. contextualize the platform content to provide a sense of community;
- 2.5. make sure the content is relevant, up to date and tailored to the use case and related users;
- 2.6. use appropriate and contextual language/communication (spoken language and formality level);
- 2.7. beware of the trade-offs between transparency and open data and privacy and security;
- 2.8. combine qualitative and quantitative data for more meaningful content;
- 2.9. invest in attractive visuals;
- 2.10. consider both the quality and quantity of engagement;
- 2.11. create a sense of trust among platform users;
- 2.12. tailor the platform features (table 2) to the use case and related users.

Figure 7: Guidelines for designing digital participation platforms.

balancing openness with privacy. Rather than prescribing fixed solutions, these guidelines serve as flexible reference points that can be adapted to different participatory contexts. They reflect both the shared concerns across actor groups and the tensions between them, offering a foundation for designing digital participation processes that are responsive, inclusive, and trustworthy.

Typology

Alongside the guidelines, we developed a typology of six digital participation platforms, categorized by their objectives, users, moderation, level of

participation, and type of content. These range from institutional tools to grassroots initiatives, illustrating the diversity of approaches in digital participation. This shows that there is no one-size-fits-all solution. Instead, digital participation tools need to be modular, adaptable, and context-sensitive, enabling meaningful engagement across different scales, communities, and governance structures.

City dashboards provide citywide data and comparative analyses to support government decision-making.

Monitoring platforms track and report on projects or programs, combining quantitative and qualitative updates.

Neighbourhood identity platforms highlight local stories and initiatives to strengthen community identity and foster collaboration.

(Spatial) survey tools gather stakeholder input through surveys, mapping, or participatory budgeting, placing citizens at the center of data collection.

Community action platforms empower residents to organize and take collective initiative, often managed by local groups.

Neighbourhood forums use informal, citizen-led or social media-based spaces to promote dialogue, mutual aid, and local initiatives.

Figure 8: Typology.

2.2

Citizen Mapping

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 Manuel Garcia Alvarez
 Selin Kubilay
 Gerdus van der Laarse
 Somdutta Sinha
 Marc Haan
 Yaren Aslan
 Johannes Ijpma

Goal

Public participation can be any process that engages the citizenry in decision-making, which can be done in diverse ways, from public hearings to online surveys. When it comes to spatial planning and design, however, public participation must go beyond conventional methods to capture spatial information from citizens and communities. A common way to obtain spatial information is through participatory mapping. Participatory mapping is a general term to identify a set of approaches and techniques that incorporate cartography into public participation to represent the spatial knowledge of local communities. Technological advances in the field of geographic information systems (GIS) have made it possible to gather and represent local knowledge in the form of digital maps. Digital participatory mapping can be used to gather data at multiple scales, from building to neighborhood, from cities to state or regional levels, as well as at different phases of urban planning, including initiation, evaluation, decision-making and scenario analysis, and maintenance. Digital participatory mapping has

the potential to reach larger numbers of participants, including vulnerable groups, complementing the existing toolbox of participatory planning methods. However, most GIS-based tools for public participation are commercial. Commercial tools tend to be expensive and may not provide the flexibility needed for research projects, for example, to include new features or modify existing ones. This project aimed at developing and testing an open-source GIS-based survey tool - the Citizen Mapping.

Try the tool!

[citizenvoice.tudelft.nl/
citizen-map/](https://citizenvoice.tudelft.nl/citizen-map/)

Research and process

The research process began with a comprehensive survey of existing participatory mapping tools, aimed at identifying the most commonly implemented features as well as those most valued by citizens. This analysis provided a foundation for understanding current design

conventions, limitations, and opportunities for innovation in participatory mapping platforms. In parallel, insights from the project No One-Size-Fits-All were integrated to inform the development of a context-sensitive design concept for what would become the Citizen Mapping

tool. These insights emphasised the importance of adaptability and inclusivity in civic technology as well as flexibility and modularity in technology development.

Building on this conceptual groundwork, a modular software architecture was designed with support from the TU Delft Digital Competence Centre (DCC). This modular approach allows new functionalities to be added incrementally, enabling the tool to evolve in response to emerging needs and specific project requirements. Software development was initiated by implementing core features first,

ensuring alignment with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles to promote transparency, reusability, and long-term sustainability.

As the tool matured, development continued in an iterative way, guided by feedback from real-world use and integrated into additional research and community-based projects, such as UP2030 and CIVILIAN. This adaptive, needs-driven approach has allowed Citizen Mapping to grow into a flexible and extensible platform that remains responsive to a diversity of contexts and stakeholders.

Output

The Citizen Mapping tool is an inclusive, web-based, open-source platform designed to gather qualitative, spatial information from citizens and local urban stakeholders. It creates a digital environment

where residents can express their perceptions, needs, and insights about the places they live in, supporting more collaborative and equitable urban planning processes. Users can respond to conventional survey questions such

as multiple choice, as well as interact with maps by adding pins or drawing polygons, linking their feedback to specific locations.

This tool is particularly suited for participatory planning sessions, whether conducted online or in person, as well as for community-led data collection efforts and remote stakeholder engagement. Its flexibility allows for tailoring engagement processes to different audiences and contexts, making it useful in both individual and group settings. By aligning participatory tasks with available technologies and the needs of stakeholders, the tool contributes to more meaningful and accessible citizen input.

amplifying the voices of vulnerable and underrepresented groups, it helps ensure that urban transformation and climate neutrality efforts reflect a broader range of lived experiences. As part of a larger ecosystem, it offers cities multiple pathways to design inclusive, tech-enabled engagement strategies.

Designed to expand participation through digital accessibility and open communication, the tool provides a reusable framework that cities can adapt to their unique challenges. In doing so, it not only strengthens the connection between governments and citizens but also serves as a reference for best practices in inclusive,

Beyond improving the quality and equity of participation, the Citizen Mapping tool also plays a strategic role in supporting climate action and socially just urban transitions. By

Figure 9: Participants testing the Citizen Mapping tool.

Figure 10: Main page of the Citizen Mapping tool.

Figure 11: Examples of questions on the Citizen Mapping tool.

UP2030

participatory urban development. As the UP2030 official website explains, UP2030 aims to help cities achieve their climate neutrality goals by supporting the socio-technical transformations needed, using urban planning and design as key levers. The project will assist city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate neutrality into both everyday actions and long-term strategic decisions. A novel methodology, the 5UP approach, will be developed and applied through the co-creation and implementation of science-based yet practical tools and methods. Inclusive participation will be central throughout all phases of the project, ensuring that community needs are genuinely reflected in each city's vision. Co-designed interventions will be crafted to maximise the delivery of co-benefits.

In doing so, UP2030 will have a measurable positive effect on spatial justice in pilot cities and provide citizens the opportunity to actively engage in the transition through sustainable behaviour changes,

positioning them as agents of change. The project also focuses on mainstreaming climate neutrality through urban planning and design as a means to enhance urban liveability. By connecting planning approaches to a broad range of social and environmental benefits, especially at the neighbourhood level, UP2030 will explore how prototyping at this scale can serve as a critical platform for innovation, reinvestment, and practical solutions. Insights gained will support scaling these efforts city-wide. To achieve broad urban impact, cities must go beyond technical solutions and pilot projects. UP2030 will equip local authorities to foster innovation-ready environments through a combination of supportive policy frameworks, inclusive participation processes, behavioural change initiatives, capacity building within city departments, new governance models, and financial mechanisms. Ultimately, UP2030 will guide cities and their stakeholders to deliver on the core values of equity, resilience, climate neutrality, and sustainability.

Figure 12: UP2030 (UP2030, n.d.).

2.3

CIVILIAN

Team members:

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 Isabella Jaramillo Diaz
 Jing Spaaij
 Virginia Facciotto

Goal

Citizen engagement is crucial for building liveable cities and for achieving climate goals. Digital platforms can play a role in the process of involving citizens, but are generally not citizen-friendly: they are not attractive to citizens and require technical expertise to act on the information from the platform (NWO, n.d.). According to Citizen Voice research, one way to make digital participatory platforms more effective is to give “data back” to citizens (Goncalves et al., 2024). Returning data empowers citizens by increasing transparency, building trust, and making participation more meaningful. When citizens can access the outcomes of their contributions, compare perspectives, and see how decisions are made, they are more likely to stay engaged. This means platforms should not only collect input but also communicate results in clear, accessible formats (Goncalves

et al., 2024). CIVILIAN is a NWO-funded project aiming at giving data collected through spatial surveys back to citizens by means of a map-based community dashboard. The dashboard is coupled with the Citizen Mapping tool and provides insights into how citizens experience their living environment.

Try the prototype!

tinyurl.com/
CIVILIANprototype

Research and process

The project started with the analysis of already existing spatial data dashboards that revealed that they are often overwhelming, difficult to navigate for non-experts, and fail to clearly communicate the relevance of the data presented. Many do not explain where the data comes from, how it is processed, or what the platform’s ownership and goals are.

To address these issues, the new dashboard was designed with three core priorities:

- **Transparency:** clearly communicating the source of the data, how it is processed, who owns the platform, and what its objectives are.
- **Accessibility:** making the interface visually appealing, intuitive, and easy to understand for everyone
- **Relevance:** showing citizens the value of their input by presenting data in a way that feels meaningful and relevant.

By providing clear, understandable, and transparent information, the dashboard aims to make citizens feel heard, demonstrate that their contributions are valued, and encourage them to participate in future surveys.

With these goals in mind, the platform was developed through two iterative prototyping and testing cycles. The design process focused on finding the right balance between clarity and visual appeal. This involved careful selection of colors, icons, and

illustrations, combined with clear language and a simple, easy-to-navigate layout. As the dashboard is integrated with the Citizen Mapping tool, a significant part of the work involved ensuring that the spatial data collected through surveys was communicated accurately and without loss of spatial context. As a result, special attention was given to map design and map-based data visualization, ensuring that geospatial insights were both preserved and clearly presented.

Output

The dashboard, which we called “Community Voices Portal”, is structured into two main sections:

Info section

This section is located in the landing page of the dashboard and serves as the introduction to the platform. It explains the purpose of the dashboard, who owns it, how the

data is processed, and invites users to either explore the map or contribute by filling out the Citizen Mapping tool survey. At the heart of this section is a custom illustration that metaphorically represents the journey of data, from collection and processing to the generation of new community projects. This visual is paired with concise and clear text that helps users understand

Figure 14: Illustration for the info section of the CIVILIAN prototype.

not only what the dashboard offers but also the value of community-generated data. The goal is to make users feel informed, included, and encouraged to take a more active role in their community.

Data visualization

Upon entering the actual dashboard, users are first shown a brief privacy statement and code of conduct, emphasizing that the data displayed comes from fellow citizens and should be used in a non-harmful way. A short tutorial follows, guiding users through how to navigate the dashboard and

interpret the different data types. The main feature is an interactive map that visualizes spatial data using a combination of colors and icons, each representing different topics. Users can toggle these layers on and off via the legend, tailoring the view to their interests. The data is represented in the form of points, lines, or areas. Some data points include citizen comments, which are indicated with text bubble-shaped icons. Hovering over these icons reveals the related note. All data displayed is fully anonymous, ensuring privacy while fostering openness and trust.

Figure 13: Participants testing the CIVILIAN prototype.

Figure 15: Data visualization section of the CIVILIAN prototype.

2.4

Citizens meet Climate

Team members:

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Carissa Champlin
Johanna Zehntner
Virginia Facciotto
Inger van Dok

Goal

Climate change is increasingly affecting urban living environments. Severe storms, sinking groundwater tables, hotter summers and milder winters are already showing their effects on infrastructure, foundations of buildings, and citizens' daily lives. In response to these climate impacts, cities have set ambitious climate targets, aiming to become climate-proof through various urban interventions. Many of these interventions require citizen support and participation, from the adoption of renewable energy to the greening of cities (e.g., roofs, backyards, etc.). Because a large part of the built environment is privately owned (about 60% in Dutch cities), the success of such initiatives depends on engaging citizens in climate action. Other strategies require people to change their behaviour and social norms. However, there is a general lack of climate risk awareness and uncertainty regarding citizens' scope of action. Many citizens do not realise how climate risks relate to their daily lives, and many more are overwhelmed and do not know how to act in times of

climate crisis. Digital climate action platforms have entered the portfolio of climate engagement strategies and have a great potential to reach larger numbers of citizens. However, existing platforms are ineffective and underutilised. This project explores the use of digital platforms to support climate engagement and develops a digital participatory platform to empower citizens to take climate action.

Try the prototype!

[tinyurl.com/
CitizensMClimate
Prototype](https://tinyurl.com/CitizensMClimatePrototype)

Figure 16: City from above with private areas highlighted (Base photo by Tom Rumble on Unsplash).

Research and process

The project started by conducting a comparative analysis of 13 existing digital platforms for public participation and climate action that led to the identification of the most common design elements employed across these platforms and analysis of their intended purposes, such as fostering engagement, informing users, or guiding their actions. This research also highlighted the main challenges of existing platforms: they lack accessibility and navigation intuitiveness, failing to provide understandable and reliable climate information. Moreover, they do not provide space for citizen users to share experiences and ideas about climate impacts and/or actions and do not provide guidance on how to take action in the real world.

At the same time, a literature review on participation processes and case studies was also conducted. This research led to the development of a six-point rubric, illustrating set of actionable design guidelines for creating effective civic platforms focused on climate. This rubric was iteratively refined over the course of the project thanks to the integration of later research findings. The six points include:

- Informing citizens and valuing their knowledge
- Balancing negative and positive framings in communication
- Providing locally, temporally, and personally relevant perspectives
- Providing tools to take both individual and collective action
- Providing clear, reliable, and open scientific data
- Including appealing and engaging elements

Having the guidelines and the problems as a foundation, the next step of the process consisted of ideating and iteratively prototyping a new digital platform aimed at empowering citizens to take climate action. The platform would have to address all identified problems and meet all rubric criteria. The design process followed three prototyping-testing cycles with a user-centred approach, from low-fidelity paper interfaces to a refined, high-fidelity digital prototype in Figma. Each iteration focused on exploring the effectiveness of the engagement strategies and in motivating citizens, the preferred tone of voice and content style, and the general accessibility and usability of the interface.

Figure 17: Participants testing the first version of the CmC prototype.

Output

Citizens meet Climate is a digital participatory platform which empowers citizens to take climate action. The platform achieves climate empowerment by:

1. Informing citizens about current and future climate risks through personalised storytelling.
2. Connecting citizens and community initiatives, creating a sense of community.
3. Listening to citizens' experiences and linking them to existing opportunities of individual and collective action in their city.

Personalization and storytelling

At the beginning of the journey, citizens select an avatar that best represents them. Each avatar represents different everyday concerns, climate awareness levels, and the ability to take climate action. The avatar guides the users on the platform through a climate story that connects climate impacts to everyday life in the present and the future, seeking a balance between a realistic and hopeful framing of the climate crisis. This feature increases the feeling of personal identification, which is essential to raising awareness about climate change while avoiding climate anxiety.

Figure 18: Personalization and storytelling elements in the CmC prototype.

Reflection on climate data

The avatar's journey exposes citizens to climate data, such as the intensity and frequency of heat waves. Data are presented in relation to the avatar's experience with climate impacts in the urban environment, creating a concrete connection between scientific data and personal experiences.

Sharing opinions with others

Throughout the journey, citizens are invited to share with other users and with the municipality their experiences and perceptions about climate impacts. This feature helps build climate literacy and awareness as citizens acknowledge the impacts of climate change on their living environment. Users can also see the opinions and perceptions of fellow citizens, creating a sense of community.

Motivation and action

At the end of the journey, citizens are invited to select a climate action initiative to help their avatar address a climate impact in the climate story. This feature presents citizens with various climate action options, individual and collective, without forcing them to take action.

The CmC prototype has been tested at various moments, receiving positive feedback. Users appreciate avatar and storytelling as well as the story timeline with present and future climate impacts. Questions about platform ownership have been raised, indicating the importance of embedding participatory tools meaningfully in decision-making processes to avoid tokenism. Since our project cannot ensure commitment to participation processes, we focus on creating opportunities for action and connections with public initiatives, and private organisations.

Suggest a new place for Alex!

This map shows the places your fellow citizens like, you can use it as inspiration for the next time you hang out in Amsterdam!

Figure 20: Sharing opinions with others elements in the CmC prototype.

What affects the temperature of our cities?

Bricks, concrete or the pavements of the inner city store heat for a much longer time than the water and open soil of parks, lakes and canals. Moreover, natural shade provided by trees in park areas prevents these places from heating up.

Figure 19: Reflection on climate data elements in the CmC prototype.

Building and DIY

Here are some great opportunities to build something that will have a positive impact on climate!

Figure 21: Motivation and action elements in the CmC prototype.

2.5

BIO-CiVo

Team members:

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Inger van Dok
Anja Overdiek
Mike Duijn

Goal

As the climate crisis deepens, the importance of biodiversity is increasingly being recognised. Large municipalities such as Rotterdam and The Hague have already implemented monitoring plans and measures to strengthen biodiversity. However, these measures often do not receive public support as citizens perceive biodiversity as complex, boring, and distant from their daily life, with an equivocal understanding that improving biodiversity is the same as increasing common greenery. Yet, citizens' efforts are needed for an integrated approach to biodiversity because roughly 60% of the urban environment is privately owned. This project takes individual and community concerns of citizens as an entry point to discuss biodiversity. It explores how map-based tools can represent citizen concerns related to local biodiversity scenarios. The research develops and studies a map-based prototype with which citizens can explore how biodiversity relates to their values and interests, to then create their own local biodiversity scenarios.

Research and process

This project adopted a research-through-design approach embedded in a participatory process to design and test interactive interfaces for citizen engagement in biodiversity action. Oud-Mathenesse was selected as the case study neighbourhood, due to the existing research network and on-going greening activities there. The project activities were organised in three work packages (WP):

- WP1 aimed at providing a prototype for scenario evaluation. The focus of this package was on interfaces for citizen interaction with a proposed biodiversity scenario. Here, we looked for the most suitable spatial scale for such interaction.
- WP2 aimed at providing a prototype for scenario building. To support citizens in the challenging task

Try the prototypes!

[tingurl.com/
BioCiVoEvaluate](https://tingurl.com/BioCiVoEvaluate)

[tingurl.com/
BioCiVoBuild](https://tingurl.com/BioCiVoBuild)

Figure 22: Participants testing the first version of the BIO-CiVo prototype.

Personalization and storytelling

The first part of the prototype is a personality test where users find out which of the 10 selected Rotterdam

species (plants or animals) match their personality. The chosen species then describes the current biodiversity threats in the neighbourhood.

Figure 23: Personalization and storytelling elements in the BIO-CiVo prototype.

of creating their own scenarios, elements that stir or hinder scenario building were identified. This package also leveraged on the findings from WP1 about scale.

- WP3 aimed at providing guidelines for the integration of the prototypes developed in WP1 and 2 into participatory approaches to biodiversity action, following the BULL framework (Slingerland, Overdiek, 2023).

Both prototypes were developed in iterative cycles and tested at various stages, with students, researchers and finally the community in Oud-Mathenesse. As a final step, the BIO-CiVo prototype was tested during the Lentefest, a community festival organised as part of the project. The prototype was made available on a Figma interactive prototype to continue support in planning biodiversity collective efforts after the research.

Output

BIO-CiVo led to the following outputs:

- Design of two digital Figma prototypes, high-fidelity, to evaluate and build local biodiversity scenarios.
- Dissemination of project and user testing of prototypes during TU Delft Dies week, AMS Scientific Conference, Citizen Science Lunch,

Lentefest, and TU Delft Climate Action Festival.

- Organisation of local community festival "Lentefest" in collaboration with citizen organisation Mathenesse aan de Maas (MaM).

Figure 24: Clear and accessible information elements in the BIO-CiVo prototype.

Clear and accessible information

In the second part, users explore two biodiversity scenarios: a concrete-based public square and a grey building façade. They are accompanied by their “personality specie”. Through multiple layers, including a layer of grass or hydroponics (for the concrete square and building façade, respectively), a layer of non-edible plants, a layer of edible plans, and a layer of people/recreational activities users can explore the biodiversity scenarios from multiple perspectives. These layers aim to illustrate different ‘types’ of green. Each layer has a set of indicators that create a biodiversity score (Biodiversity Thermometer), including water usage, maintenance, multifunctional space usage, heat stress, and construction cost. The layers fit on top of each other, creating a full biodiversity scenario. Partial scenarios can also be assessed by combinations of 2 or 3 layers.

Sharing opinions

Finally, the last part of the prototype asks users to evaluate the scenario.

Users first evaluate the value of the current situation (i.e., the concrete square and the grey building façade) by giving it a score between 1 and 5. Then, they describe what activities they imagine they would do here if this place were in their neighbourhood. They are also asked to rank the layers by importance, choose which layers to implement, and evaluate how valuable each layer is to their neighbourhood. A box for suggestions is also provided.

Designing their own scenarios

As a next step, users are guided to the second prototype, where they can start creating their own biodiversity scenario. They are also offered the opportunity to connect with local initiatives for biodiversity, to start implementing an existing or a new scenario. The scenario designing happens in an abstract environment and uses the same design elements (layers and thermometer) to create and give some feedback on the design. This scenario can then be evaluated by other users as explained before.

Figure 26: Sharing opinions elements in the BIO-CiVo prototype.

Lentefest

As the culminating public moment of the BIO-CiVo project, the Lentefest (Spring Festival) held on May 25th, 2024, in Serumpark (Oud-Mathenesse, Rotterdam) offered an ideal setting to engage directly with residents in a festive, informal atmosphere. Co-organised by student assistants from the Citizen Voice team and local residents from the citizen organisation Mathenesse aan de Maas (MaM), the event served both as a celebration of local culture and a testbed for the final version of the biodiversity prototype. Approximately 150 visitors attended the festival, which featured 23 booths, including ten showcasing green initiatives, a diverse food program prepared by residents, and live performances by

local bands. This setting enabled easy access to participate in the testing and meaningful interaction with the prototype. During the preparation, feedback from a local resident helped contextualise the scenarios and inform important adjustments to the prototype. At the festival, visitors from all ages explored the tools and engaged in conversations about biodiversity. The presence of Mayor Aboutaleb, who engaged with various booths and initiatives, further validated the relevance of local voices in shaping biodiversity policy. Through this setting, the Lentefest illustrated how biodiversity can be brought closer to people’s everyday concerns and neighbourhood dynamics.

Figure 25: Designing their own scenario elements in the BIO-CiVo prototype.

Figure 27: Pictures from the Lentefest.

2.6

ParticipAlte

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 Robin Smits
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 Valentina Guadagno
 Virginia Facciotto
 Yara Boom

Goal and process

ParticipAlte is a speculative design project that explores the role of artificial intelligence in the future of public participation. Rather than aiming to deliver definitive solutions, the project critically examines both the opportunities and challenges that emerging technologies present in this context. Its goal is to uncover the complexity of the topic and encourage viewers to reflect on it. The project originated as a master's course assignment within the Interactive Technology Design course, part of the Design for Interaction program at the Faculty of Industrial

Design Engineering, TU Delft. In this course, students engaged with the theme through a research-through-design approach, developing and testing multiple prototypes to investigate a variety of research questions. As part of the course, three final design concepts and prototypes were developed: Bruno the bench, Under the Loop, and kAlte. These concepts were later refined and brought together into a cohesive installation named ParticipAlte, which was showcased at the CityClimate meets CreativeCoding (CCmCC) festival in Hamburg, Germany, in 2023.

Figure 28: Pictures from the students' midterm presentation.

Figure 29: The ParticipAlte installation at the CCmCC festival.

Output

ParticipAlte is an interactive installation that brings together the three speculative concepts, Bruno the bench, Under the Loop, and kAlte, to explore the potential role of AI in future public participation processes. The installation aims to highlight the flow of citizen-generated data from neighborhood buzz into a high-stakes municipal board room. It presents a critical and speculative vision of how AI might mediate and amplify public voices in urban planning.

The installation uses Rotterdam as an experimental site. By the year 2070, parts of Rotterdam will experience frequent flooding caused by rising sea levels and intense heavy rainfall events. The Municipality will have to choose between several courses of action to address the issue: from raising the level of the dikes to redesigning low-lying areas into floating neighborhoods. ParticipAlte presents the dilemmas of people living in a Rotterdam neighborhood who are grappling with an uncertain future for their community. By embedding AI into a fictional citizen engagement process, the installation explores how community values, local knowledge, and speculative technologies might converge to shape inclusive, participatory urban futures.

Bruno the bench

Today, only a select few hold the power in city-making and an important number of citizens don't participate in this activity. Bruno the bench aims at involving citizens in this decision-making process through a platform that allows accessibility and treats them as an expert of their own neighborhood.

Bruno is an inanimate city object that is transformed into a conversational tool that people can encounter in frequently visited public spaces, allowing them to participate and

gain control of their future. Like him, benches, trash bins, even buildings can be given a voice. Citizens engage in personal conversations with these objects of the city and share their opinions and ideas on the physical and social aspects of the neighborhood that the object is located in. Through these conversations with the inanimate, people foster empathy and a deeper understanding of how their surroundings look and behave which strengthens their bond with the environment, its people, its space and its things.

Figure 30: Bruno the bench.

Through these talking objects, urban planners can stay connected to citizens' stories and their needs perpetually. By actively listening and incorporating these narratives, urban planners can create more inclusive and responsive cities. Bruno is basically a mediator for creating a collective vision for the future city.

Bruno the Bench is powered by AI and is programmed by planners, but it constantly adapts its behavior based on the input received during conversations, similar to how people mirror and adjust their interactive behavior constantly.

Urban planners can select an object from a popular spot in the neighborhood that aligns with the upcoming city plans about which they need citizens' input. Multiple objects can be active simultaneously, ensuring an ongoing exchange of data for as long as the planners require.

Under the Loop

Under the Loop aims to facilitate a constructive dialogue among citizens, urban planners, and key stakeholders, including municipal authorities by providing an opportunity for people to easily and actively participate to

Figure 31: Under the Loop

Figure 32: kAlte

shape their environment. It builds on the belief that initiating citizen involvement as early as possible in the planning process can allow numerous benefits, because citizens are the unique experts in the embodied experiences of living within their communities, allowing them to offer meaningful and relevant input on city pain points. Under the Loop is designed to engage pioneers—individuals eager to express their opinions and question the current state of their environment. It also prompts us to consider how AI-driven artifacts can empower individuals to assume greater ownership of their everyday surroundings and encourage them to reflect on their role in city development.

Under the Loop serves a dual purpose: it enables citizens to share their perspectives on the city and functions as a research tool that helps fill gaps

in our understanding of participatory urban planning. Using this device, individuals can express their thoughts and concerns, supported by data gathered from integrated sensors. This personalized and customizable device allows citizens to respond to prompts from the local government about specific locations or share their opinions voluntarily. These insights, worries, and noteworthy observations are systematically collected and analyzed by artificial intelligence within an open-source network hosted by municipal authorities.

Under the Loop is equipped with various sensors to gather data and actuators to provide feedback to all stakeholders involved in city planning decision making. Various user groups can select and incorporate different sensors to tailor the device to their specific needs. By incorporating AI technology, it adopts a new approach

to participation that integrates community values and local insights into urban planning and decision-making processes.

kAlte

Governing parties such as urban planners and civil servants often speak about citizens instead of with citizens. Asking citizens about their opinion, dreams and concerns, or what they are in need to achieve their goals is a crucial first step towards a more social and just society. The public debate serves policy makers and citizens with a loud voice very well, while the largest group is often unheard. Thus citizens should be able to participate in various different ways, making it accessible for all, and all voices should be heard. Citizen input in the form of demographic

factual information is currently the 'language' that dominates. This kind of data is a limited translation of reality because it tells nothing about people's values, beliefs and current or desired habits. As cities behave like large living organisms, being complex and networked, the empathic tensions should also be present in local city meetings.

kAlte is an AI system that enables and represents multilevel citizen participation. A large number of citizens are reached through different modes of collection, depending on the type of project. Based on keyword categorization, the AI system combines and differentiates all inputs while maintaining nuance. kAlte takes its place as a new stakeholder in local city meetings, bringing in the voices of carefully compiled personas of

citizens. kAlte projects a geographical map and contributes to the meeting by both talking and controlling the map. kAlte uses light and sound to communicate if and when it is active, listening and speaking. Attendees see kAlte (and thus citizens) as an equal partner to design with, rather than to design for. Therefore, kAlte is embodied at the same hierarchical level. Listening to the conversations

of attendees of a local city meeting, kAlte enters the conversation when it is relevant. As it knows all citizens it will make certain personas audible that were underrepresented thus far. The attendees do not control kAlte, but can talk with it and ask questions or request it to collect certain data. At times, kAlte will incentivize to engage with the citizens in real life.

Figure 33: kAlte

Figure 34: kAlte

2.7

Meeting Spatial Justice

Team members:

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 Juliana Gonçalves
 Roberto Rocco

Goal

As part of a collaborative effort between Citizen Voice (TU Delft) and The Hague University of Applied Sciences, and within the European UP2030 project, Meeting Spatial Justice explores how an introductory, digital reflection tool can foster attention to justice within climate-neutral urban planning in Dutch municipalities. The tool will complement existing resources in the package, including the Spatial Justice Handbook and the Spatial Justice Benchmark.

The project investigates how municipal actors perceive, reflect on, and engage with justice in local planning contexts. The tool's goal is to embed reflection moments in existing workflows, so speaking up feels safe and justice becomes a normal part of decisions in a way that the tool supports exploratory, reflective learning rather than prescribed solutions.

The project is expected to be completed by late October 2025.

Research and process

The project follows a UX and research-through-design approach, combining qualitative methods (interviews, co-design sessions) with iterative prototyping. Research is conducted with municipal professionals, advisors, students/practitioners in urban planning, and designers from around the world.

Sprint 1: Discovery and framing

The project began with seven field interviews, where 160 statements were translated into data cards and coded as barriers or enablers of reflection. Each card was then plotted in the COM-B / TDF model (Michie, Atkins, West, 2014), a behaviour-change framework that explains any behaviour as the result of Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation (COM-B), and unpacks these into practical domains via the Theoretical Domains Framework (e.g., knowledge, skills, social influences, environmental

context, beliefs about consequences). Using COM-B/TDF here is helpful because it turns qualitative insights into actionable levers: it shows whether reflection on justice is limited by skills/knowledge (capability), by context and social dynamics (opportunity), or by meaning, goals and habits (motivation).

Afterwards, cards were clustered through an affinity diagram, producing twelve core findings about how justice currently appears in municipal practice, for example, that reflection works when it is built into workflow, that team culture and power dynamics shape the learning climate, and that connection is more powerful than persuasion. The synthesis showed that while many blockers sit in Physical Opportunity (Environmental Context), the most feasible leverage for this project lies in Social Opportunity and Reflective Motivation, with Psychological Capability and Automatic Motivation providing supporting roles.

Figure 35: Examples of COM-B / TDF model in use.

Sprint 2: Benchmarking and co-design

In parallel, a benchmark of existing reflection/learning frameworks was mapped to COM-B / TDF to identify formats that could realistically fit municipal routines. In alignment with Phase 1 insights, three frameworks were selected: De Haagse Participatiewijze (by The Hague Municipality), Focused Conversations (by Facilitation Dev), and Acting in Alignment (by Transition Makers). Four research-through-design interviews then examined which design elements could best match the project goals.

The work proceeds to an online co-design session with 8-10 participants, primarily impact experience and interaction designers from around the world, to ideate the possibilities of execution. Afterwards, the design direction will be formalized and the

final prototyping phase will begin. At the time of writing, this phase is underway.

Sprint 3: Prototyping and testing

Low to mid-fidelity prototypes will be designed and tested in short cycles with municipal team-members. Evaluation will focus on practicality, safety, and usefulness, specifically: perceived psychological safety (can people speak up?), clarity of consequences, accessibility of language (participants' literacy level), and repeatability within current planning workflows. Findings will inform the final iterations toward a Meeting Spatial Justice tool that complements the Spatial Justice Handbook and the Spatial Justice Benchmark.

Figure 36: Examples of prototypes used to do research-through-design.

Impact

This chapter presents Citizen Voice's commitment to create a wide range of positive impact. Through events, open-source practices, research, and public engagement, we work to create processes that are transparent, trustworthy, and adaptable, ensuring that participation not only informs better decisions but also strengthens communities and civic trust.

Introduction

When citizens and communities speak, share, and act, cities become more just, vibrant, and resilient. We therefore stand for decisions grounded in lived experience, where the knowledge of residents guides policies, plans, and designs. We embrace digital tools to expand participation and open the door to new voices, ensuring inclusivity in every step, but remain critical of their impacts and limitations. We commit to creating processes that are open, transparent, and accountable, where every voice can be heard, and where resources serve those who need them most. Above all, we believe that participation builds trust, and trust builds communities.

Local perspectives help ensure that planning and design remains sensitive to environmental, cultural, and social contexts. By involving residents directly, decision-makers gain access to invaluable on-the-ground insights, leading to decisions and designs that are more relevant and responsive to real community needs.

Participation also strengthens accountability and transparency, ensuring that resources are allocated more effectively and that public services respond to the lived realities of communities. This process also enhances legitimacy and acceptance, as people are more likely to support and trust policies they have helped shape.

At the same time, inclusive processes build civic engagement and trust, inspiring citizens to remain active in public life. Working together fosters a sense of solidarity and shared identity, while also empowering individuals with new skills and knowledge about how to influence change.

We therefore strive to create a wide range of positive impacts that extend far beyond selected projects and outputs. This includes outreach efforts and open repositories as well as academic and media presence.

Figure 38: Citizen Voice Launch Event.

Figure 37: Citizen Voice Launch Event.

Citizen Voice launch event

In April 2025, we hosted our first major event, bringing together over 50 academics, practitioners, and students from diverse disciplines. Together, we explored questions at the intersections of citizen and community engagement in planning and design, digital participation technologies and open science, and transdisciplinary and participatory research. The event also featured an interactive exhibition, where participants had the opportunity to engage with our digital prototypes and a mini-version of the ParticipAlte installation. The workshop fostered rich discussions on barriers, enablers, and emerging trends in these areas, culminating in a collective

position paper: "Citizen Voice in Action: Insights on Public Participation, Digital Technologies, and Transdisciplinarity in Urban Research and Practice." Beyond the formal outcomes, the event was celebrated for its warm, collegial atmosphere and the depth of dialogue it inspired. Participants valued the opportunity to connect across fields, and students especially expressed enthusiasm for the themes, noting how rarely such perspectives are addressed in current curricula. The energy and ideas shared during the day continue to fuel ongoing collaborations and inspire new approaches to participatory urban research and practice.

Figure 39: Groups discussing at the Citizen Voice launch event.

Open access

Our mission to create meaningful societal impact is inseparable from our commitment to open access. We believe that knowledge, tools, and data should be shared widely so they can be built upon, adapted, and applied in diverse contexts beyond our own work. To ensure transparency and reproducibility, we maintain an open GitHub repository containing the source code of our tools. This allows researchers, practitioners, and community members to inspect, reuse, and improve our solutions, fostering collective innovation.

Complementing our code repository, we use Zenodo to host and share other outputs of our work, such as reports, academic outputs, and supporting materials. Zenodo provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) to ensure long-term accessibility and citability, enabling others to reference and integrate our contributions into their own projects. Through these open access practices, we aim not only to advance our own research goals but also to empower others to address challenges, adapt our methods, and amplify impact across disciplines and sectors.

Links to our materials

Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/tudelftcitizenvoice>

GitHub:
<https://github.com/Citizens-Collective>

Academic impact

Event: Climate Action Festival

On June 10th, the TU Delft Climate Action Programme held its first Climate Action Festival, bringing together over 100 researchers, innovators, and environmental enthusiasts. The event was a great success, promoting collaboration and inspiring sustainable action. Citizen Voice was present with a demonstrator, presenting our tools and insights into how to engage citizens in urban climate action.

Event: TU Delft Science Day

The Science Day is the day when the TU Delft Campus transforms into one large world of discovery. Every year, we welcome thousands of visitors and explore the fascinating world of science and technology together. Citizen Voice participated in the 2025 edition

Workshop: Digital Engagement in Times of Climate Crisis

The workshop was informed by insights from the CmC and BioCiVo projects. Approximately 20 attendees explored our prototypes and contributed their own experiences with tools, methods, and platforms related to citizen science, community engagement, and biodiversity initiatives. These insights were crucial in both projects to advance our understanding of how people engage with technology.

Presentation: Citizen Voices in Climate Action: The role of interface design in digital engagement @ Reinventing the City AMS conference 2024

This presentation shared preliminary results from the CmC and BioCiVo projects, focusing on citizen

Figure 42: Drawings made by children at the TU Delft Science Day.

engagement in climate action. Taking a user-centred approach to analyse over ten digital platforms, we explored the research question of what supports or hinders citizens from participation in climate action. From this analysis, we developed design guidelines across four themes: awareness and framing, supporting individual and collective action, effective use of data, and clear navigation and visuals. These

guidelines were used in the prototypes developed in CmC and BioCiVo. The presentation can be found on Citizen Voice's Zenodo folder.

Workshop: I'm not a human sensor! @ Reinventing the City AMS conference 2024

The workshop drew on the CmC and BioCiVo projects. Around 15 participants had the opportunity to engage with

Figure 40: Citizen Voice at Climate Action Festival and TU Delft Science Day.

Figure 41: Poster of the 'Digital Engagement in Times of Climate Crisis' workshop.

our prototypes and share examples of tools, approaches, and platforms they had used in citizen science, participation, and biodiversity projects. Together, we mapped existing platforms, discussed their applications in citizen science processes, identified common challenges, and brainstormed potential solutions.

Paper: No-one-size-fits-all

Gonçalves, J. E., Ioannou, I., & Verma, T. (2024). No one-size-fits-all: Multi-actor perspectives on public participation and digital participatory platforms. *Philosophical Transactions A*, 382(2285), 20240111. 10.1098/rsta.2024.0111

MSc thesis: Urban Voices

Ioannou, I. (2022). Urban Voices. Citizen Voice: An innovative Open-source Map-based tool for effective public participation. <https://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:4a44c02e-57a1-4e26-8e53-b942c5dd9ecf>

Figure 43: Citizen Voice's workshop at Reinventing the City AMS conference.

Figure 44: Citizen Voice at Reinventing the City AMS conference.

In the media

2023

2024

DREAM.DISCOVER.DESIGN.
October 2023, Eindhoven

Exhibition curated by TU Delft - Industrial Design Engineering at Dutch Design Week 2023. Bruno the bench (part of the ParticipAlte project) was exhibited in this event.

www.tudelft.nl/en/2023/10/november/dreamdiscoverdesign

Citizens meet Climate: Empowering Citizens in Climate Action
Featured in Design United, 4TU

CmC was featured in the magazine that enhances the innovative strength of the Dutch creative industry by bridging the gap between design research and the design community.

www.4tu.nl/du/projects/Citizens-meet-Climate-Empowering-Citizens-in-Climate-Action/

CityClimate meets CreativeCoding
October 2023, Hamburg

Three-day excursion of the intersections of art, science and climate data featured international and Hamburg-based art works, projects, workshops, serious games and experiments. The ParticipAlte project was exhibited in this event.

www.citysciencelab.hamburg/projects/ccmcc

Digital tools foster citizen engagement on urban climate action
Interview by Citizen Science, TU Delft

Juliana Gonçalves and Geertje Slingerland discuss the opportunities and limitations of using digital technologies for citizen engagement.

www.tudelft.nl/en/citizen-science/blog/digital-tools-foster-citizen-engagement-on-urban-climate-action

Giving citizens a voice in local biodiversity
Interview by Research Stories, TU Delft

Our team reflects on the process and insights from the BIO-CiVo project, which focuses on understanding how citizens engage with urban biodiversity through the use of digital tools.

www.tudelft.nl/en/architecture-and-the-built-environment/research/research-stories/giving-citizens-a-voice-in-local-biodiversity

Figure 45: Bruno the bench at Dutch Design Week 2023.

Figure 46: CityClimate meets CreativeCoding Festival.

4

Ethical guidelines

This chapter details our approach to ethics and our ethical guidelines. Including ethical principles for creating engagement surveys and suggestions for survey creators and respondents.

Introduction

Purpose

The development of ethical guidelines for citizen engagement surveys is essential to ensure integrity, respect, and fairness in participatory urban planning processes. Surveys serve as key instruments for gathering the voices of diverse communities, and ethical considerations must guide their design and implementation. These guidelines are especially relevant when working with digital tools, which present both opportunities and challenges in maintaining trust, equity, and privacy.

Context: growing importance of participatory urban planning

Participatory urban planning is becoming increasingly central to the

design of inclusive and sustainable cities. It empowers citizens to meaningfully influence decisions about their environments. However, the quality of participation depends on ethical, transparent, and thoughtful engagement practices. While digital technologies have broadened the reach and flexibility of participatory tools, they have also introduced new ethical challenges related to accessibility, data ownership, and equitable inclusion. The ethical principles outlined in this document have been developed through the ongoing work of the Citizen Voice initiative, which has identified key factors necessary for maintaining ethical integrity in participatory processes.

Ethical principles for citizen engagement surveys

These are normative values that should guide all aspects of the survey process, whether you're designing, deploying, or analyzing.

“What core ethical values should we uphold when engaging citizens?”

Ethical principles are the foundation of responsible citizen engagement, especially in contexts involving data collection, digital tools, and participatory decision-making. These guidelines are important because they help safeguard the dignity, rights, and voices of individuals who contribute to

planning processes. They ensure that participation is not only effective but also fair and respectful. These principles are intended for researchers, practitioners, city officials, designers, and anyone involved in conducting or facilitating engagement surveys. Whether you are designing, deploying, or analyzing a survey, these high-level, normative values serve as a compass to guide ethical choices and uphold public trust in participatory processes.

Transparency

- Clearly explain why you are involving people and what decisions will be made.
- Show how the process works, step by step, in a way everyone can understand.
- Don't just involve people as a formality. Show them how their opinions actually influence decisions.

Informed consent and privacy

- Tell participants what data you collect, why you collect it, and what will happen with it.
- Let people join anonymously if possible.
- Allow them to leave at any time without negative consequences.
- Be clear about who owns the data and if it will be shared or published.

Inclusivity and accessibility

- Use simple, inclusive language and different formats like audio, video, or pictures.
- Provide translations, accessible designs, and technical support for everyone.
- Think about digital skills and physical or mental disabilities when designing your tools and activities.
- Reduce barriers by offering things like childcare, transport help, flexible meeting times, or trusted community contacts.

Trust and reciprocity

- Work with local community leaders or organisations who can connect you with people.
- Always communicate back to participants what decisions were made and how their input helped, in clear language.
- Engage in continuous cycles: inform people, gather their input, reflect on it, adapt your plans, and keep them updated.

Open knowledge sharing

- Share your methods, tools, and findings so others can learn and build on your work.
- This avoids repeating the same work and encourages new ideas and solutions.
- Use open-source platforms whenever you can, to keep the process transparent and collaborative.

Ethical oversight

- Researchers must follow their university's ethics guidelines.
- Collaborators from other organisations should check with their own ethics committees.
- Treat ethics as an ongoing and reflective process, not just a form to fill out.

Figure 47: Material from a workshop.

Guidelines for survey creators

These are concrete, practical instructions tailored to the different stages of building and conducting a survey. They answer the question:

“What should I do, step by step, to ensure the survey is ethically sound?”

Before designing the survey

- **Co-Define Goals:** Collaborate with community partners to define the survey’s purpose, scope, and expectations. Ensure alignment on whether the aim of participation is democratic engagement or problem-solving. Engage in clear communication, trust, and transparency from the outset to build mutual understanding and accountability.
- **Design for Equity:** Apply universal design principles that accommodate diverse levels of education, language proficiency, and access to technology. Participation should be relevant to the everyday lives of citizens and tailored to the specific context and needs of the groups involved. Consider both formal and informal communication styles to reduce risks of exclusion or stigmatization.
- **Anticipate Risks:** Identify and address power imbalances that may affect participation. Recognize the potential harms, including the risks of stigmatization, and plan to mitigate them through inclusive processes and moderation/facilitation strategies that ensure all voices are heard.
- **Plan for Compensation:** Acknowledge and fairly compensate the time, knowledge, and lived experiences of participants, especially those from marginalized

communities. Be transparent about the basis of compensation, recognizing the tension between extrinsic and intrinsic motivations.

- **Establish Feedback Mechanisms:** Design the survey with built-in feedback loops to communicate outcomes clearly and maintain engagement over time. Emphasize responsiveness and continuity as ongoing commitments. Where possible, develop new partnerships and support local networks to sustain dialogue beyond the survey period.

During survey deployment

- **Support Participation:** Provide both human and technological assistance to ensure accessibility for all participants. Consider the use of moderators or facilitators to guide participation, reduce misunderstandings, and foster a welcoming environment, especially in settings with varying levels of familiarity with digital tools.
- **Ensure Anonymity Options:** Offer the ability for respondents to remain anonymous and clarify how their data will be handled. Address expectation management by setting clear boundaries for privacy, influence, and use of information.
- **Communicate Clearly:** Explain the survey’s purpose, estimated time commitment, and voluntary nature in plain, inclusive language. Aim for clear communication, transparency, and trust-building to foster confidence in the process. Consider the tone, formal or informal, depending on the context, to avoid alienating any groups.
- **Respond to Concerns:** Provide timely responses to participant

questions or issues during the survey. Actively monitor participation levels and flag possible challenges such as technical access barriers or feelings of exclusion. Recognize that being included is not the same as feeling genuinely engaged or influential in the process.

- **Promote Inclusiveness:** Use a mix of digital and physical participation modes where possible. Ensure the process accommodates different levels of tech access and comfort, recognizing contextual needs and use cases. Leverage top-down and bottom-up approaches to avoid power imbalances.

After the survey

- **Close the Feedback Loop:** Publish results in accessible, plain-language formats that reach the participants and wider public. Share not only what was said but how it influenced decisions, maintaining continuity and responsiveness. Reaffirm transparency by making clear how feedback shaped actions.
- **Document Impact:** Clearly state how the findings shaped outcomes. Link this process back to the multi-dimensional assessment of effectiveness, capturing both outcomes and how inclusive or

engaging the process was. This ensures public participation is seen as meaningful, not symbolic.

- **Store Data Responsibly:** Ensure data is securely stored and anonymized before any form of sharing or analysis. Respect privacy and institutional commitments to ethical stewardship of community knowledge.
- **Reflect and Learn:** Conduct internal reviews to assess what worked and what didn’t. Evaluate both the process and the outcomes, and update your practices accordingly. Build and share a knowledge base that supports a more equitable playing field in future participatory work.

Practical guidelines:

- You are a guest; **always be respectful.**
- Introduce yourself as a student (students are generally seen as approachable).
- **Manage expectations:** explain clearly the purpose of your street interviews.
- Think carefully about your words to **avoid stigmatizing** anyone.
- If people don’t want to participate, **don’t take it personally.** Stay polite and thank them for their time.

Figure 48: User test.

Guidelines for survey respondents

These are recommendations designed to help individuals understand their rights and responsibilities when participating in a survey. They answer the question:

“What should I know and do to participate ethically, safely, and meaningfully in a citizen engagement survey?”

Before participating

- **Understand the Survey Purpose:** Know what the survey aims to achieve, what topics it will cover, and how your responses will be used. A good process will share clear and transparent communication upfront. Look for information about who is conducting the survey and what decisions it may inform.
- **Clarify Your Rights:** You have the right to participate voluntarily, decline to answer any question, and exit the survey at any time. Ensure you understand how your anonymity and confidentiality will be protected.
- **Assess Relevance to Your Life:** Surveys should aim to connect to the everyday experiences of citizens. If something feels disconnected or unclear, you are encouraged to seek clarification before beginning.

During participation

- **Engage Authentically:** Provide honest, thoughtful responses. Feeling included is not just about being asked, it’s about knowing your voice matters. Your lived experience can shape better decisions.
- **Ask for Help If Needed:** If a question is confusing, too technical,

or not accessible to you (e.g. due to language or format), ask for clarification or assistance. Effective surveys often have moderators or facilitators who can help.

- **Know You Have Influence:** Participation should not feel symbolic. Ethical surveys aim to ensure inclusiveness and create opportunities for you to influence the process, not just complete a form.

After participation

- **Stay Informed:** You can ask how your input contributed to the final results. Feedback loops, where findings are shared with participants, are a sign of respect and accountability in public participation.
- **Give Feedback:** Your experience matters. Sharing what worked and what didn’t helps make future surveys more inclusive, accessible, and engaging. Some organizations also review the process to learn and improve.
- **Look for Outcomes:** Watch for how the results of the survey are shared or used. Surveys committed to transparency, responsiveness, and continuity will show how your voice contributed to change.

Final recommendations

1

Embed Ethics Early and Often: Ethical engagement must begin at the design stage and evolve continuously.

2

Value Citizen Contributions: Compensate time and insights, and show respect for all participants.

3

Build Ethical Infrastructure: Develop flexible ethics protocols that accommodate digital and experimental approaches.

4

Train Practitioners: Invest in education and training around participatory methods, especially digital and inclusive tools.

5

Recognize Diverse Stakeholders: Include voices often left out of traditional processes, especially “silent stakeholders” like nature or future generations.

6

Design Beyond Compliance: View ethical engagement not as a box-checking task but as a deeply relational, long-term process.

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